

Consent

"I agree to work on questionnaires and tasks related to the applicability of certain practices in research projects.

I agree with the described collection and processing of data (questionnaires, task results). The recording and evaluation of the data are done anonymously at the University of Tübingen (Germany), i.e. it is not possible for anyone to associate my data with my name. I agree that my anonymized data may be used for research purposes, may be stored for at least 10 years, and may be made publicly accessible in completely anonymized form (i.e. without information on age, gender, and education) for further use.

I had sufficient time to make a decision and I am willing to participate in the study. I know that participation in the study is voluntary and that I can terminate my participation at any time without giving reasons.

If I have questions or other concerns, I can contact the following person: Jürgen Schneider
juergen.schneider[at]uni-tuebingen.de."